

growth medium (Table 1). SG36 showed marked growth reduction.

XZN 1 absorbed more Cu, Mn, Fe, K, Na, Mg, and Ca from the K-deficient growth medium (Table 2). SG36 increased absorption of only Zn, Mg, Na, and Ca. Fe and K absorption by XZN 1 was higher than that by SG36, but SG36 absorbed more Zn and Na.

It appears that in XZN 1, Fe, Mn, Mg, Na, and Ca substituted for K. These clear varietal differences in adaptability to low K availability indicates that breeding for K-deficient soils should be possible. ■

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.

Table 1. Dry weight of seedlings grown in complete and K-deficient nutrient solutions

Days after sowing	Dry weight (mg/plant)			
	XZN 1		SG36	
	Complete	Deficient	Complete	Deficient
34	34.0	36.0	36.0	29.0
38	129.0	124.0	125.0	74.0
41	135.0	135.0	135.0	88.0

Table 2. Mineral content of 38-d-old shoots.

Element	Content (% dry weight)			
	XZN 1		SG36	
	Complete	Deficient	Complete	Deficient
Cu	2.0×10^{-3}	2.3×10^{-3}	1.8×10^{-3}	2.3×10^{-3}
Mn	9.5×10^{-3}	1.0×10^{-2}	2.4×10^{-2}	1.1×10^{-2}
Zn	2.5×10^{-2}	3.1×10^{-2}	4.3×10^{-2}	4.7×10^{-2}
Fe ^a	3.8×10^{-2}	4.4×10^{-2}	4.3×10^{-2}	3.6×10^{-2}
Mg	0.40	0.65	0.58	0.77
K	3.09	1.49	2.93	0.63
Na	6.3×10^{-2}	0.24	0.12	0.76
Ca ^a	0.23	0.29	0.20	0.30

^aSampled 50 d after sowing.

Integrated germplasm improvement—general

CO 45, a new, medium-duration rice variety for Tamil Nadu

S. Palanisamy, T. B. Ranganathan, S. R. S. Rangasamy, V. Sivasubramanian, G. A. Palanisamy, W. W. Manuel, S. M. Lal, and K. Natarajamoorthy, Paddy Breeding Station (PBS), Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, Tamil Nadu, India

TNAU80042 (IR17492-18-10-2-2-2) is a derivative of Rathu Heenati/IR3403-

267-1. It was named CO 45 and released in Jan 1990 for general cultivation in Tamil Nadu. It can be used as an alternate to IR20 and CO 43 in the second crop season (Sep-Oct).

CO 45 is 75-80 cm tall and matures in 140 d. Grain is long and slender with white rice.

It yielded an average 5.9 t/ha (10% more than CO 43) in breeding station trials 1980-81 to 1988-89. In multilocation trials 1985-86 to 1988-89, it yielded 4.1% higher than CO 43 and 14.9%

higher than IR20. In adaptive research trials in 10 districts 1987-88 to 1988-89, it yielded 10% higher than CO 43. In national trials 1985 and 1987, it yielded 17% more than Jaya and Pankaj (see table).

CO 45 is resistant to green leafhopper, stem borer, blast, bacterial blight, and tungro, and moderately resistant to sheath rot (panicle exertion is better than that of sheath rot-susceptible CO 43). ■

Chandan, a multiple-resistance variety released in Andhra Pradesh

M. Kashikar, V. Hasan, R. V. Kumar, N. Kulkarni, S. Banu, and H. S. N. Rao, Agricultural Research Institute, A. P. Agricultural University, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030. Andhra Pradesh, India

RNR74802, a semidwarf medium-duration culture derived from Sona/Manoharsali, was released in Sep 1989 as Chandan. It is recommended for general cultivation in Andhra Pradesh.

In yield trials in 1977-87, RNR74802 averaged 5.6 t/ha. That is 35% higher

Performance of CO 45 in Tamil Nadu, India, 1980-89.

Location	Grain yield (t/ha)					Increase (%)			
	CO 45	CO 43	IR20	Jaya	Pankaj	CO 43	IR20	Jaya	Pankaj
Breeding station									
Coimbatore (1980-81 to 1988-89)	5.8	5.3	-	-	-	10	-	-	-
Multilocation trials (1985-86 to 1988-89)	4.8	4.6	4.2	-	-	4	15	-	-
Adaptive research trials (1987-88)	5.8	5.6	5.4	-	-	4	7	-	-
Adaptive research trials (1988-89)	6.2	5.4	5.2	-	-	15	19	-	-
National trials (AICRIP 1985)	5.0	-	-	4.3	-	-	-	17	-
National trials (AICRIP 1987)	5.3	-	-	-	4.5	-	-	-	18